

CERTAINTY UHMI's DMP

Version 0

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Enviro-HIRLAM and WRF data created at the UHMI is developed in the context of effective management and processing data generated for CERTAINTY project.

The DMP for the Enviro-HIRLAM and WRF data at the UHMI is designed to maximize value, accessibility and impact of the data produced supporting the institute's mission in advancing meteorological research and services.

Funder

European Commission||EC

Grant

Cloud-aERosol inTeractions &
their impActs IN The earth
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Researchers

Larysa Pysarenko (orcid:0000-0002-2885-0213), Anastasiia
Chyhareva (orcid:0000-0003-0195-751X), Svitlana Krakovska
(orcid:0000-0001-9972-0937), Liudmyla Nadtochii
(orcid:0000-0003-3038-5960), Mykhailo Savenets
(orcid:0000-0001-9429-6209)

Organizations

Ukrainian Hydrometeorological Institute

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: CERTAINTY UHMI's DMP

Description:

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Enviro-HIRLAM and WRF data created at the UHMI is developed in the context of effective management and processing data generated for CERTAINTY project.

The DMP for the Enviro-HIRLAM and WRF data at the UHMI is designed to maximize value, accessibility and impact of the data produced supporting the institute's mission in advancing meteorological research and services.

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Anastasiia Chyhareva (orcid:0000-0003-0195-751X)
Svitlana Krakovska (orcid:0000-0001-9972-0937)
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Organizations:

Ukrainian Hydrometeorological Institute

Contact: Mykhailo Savenets

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission|EC

Grants: Cloud-aERosol inTeractions & their impActs IN The earth sYstem

Project: Cloud-aERosol inTeractions & their impActs IN The earth sYstem

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Enviro-HIRLAM output

Online-integrated modeling on a regional scale for studying aerosol-cloud interactions, direct and indirect aerosol effects during extreme weather events

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

A set of simulated meteorological parameters and aerosol compounds.

1.1.5 What is its format?

GRIB, NetCDF

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1 250 000 000 000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To combine with other data

Data will be used to study aerosol-cloud interactions, direct and indirect aerosol effects

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Enviro-HIRLAM. The Enviro-HIRLAM modelling system is a community model. The source code is available for non-commercial use (i.e. research, development, and science education) upon agreement through contact with Alexander Mahura (alexander.mahura@helsinki.fi), Bent Sass (bhs@dmi.dk), and Roman Nuterman (nuterman@nbi.ku.dk). Documentation are available from <http://hirlam.org>, <http://hirlam.org/index.php/documentation/chemistry-branch> (login required)

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education

Project partners, scientific community in Atmospheric Sciences, national meteorological services, for students, who study atmospheric modeling, as educational data.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

Description Metadata of the Enviro-HIRLAM output with the data of state meteorological variables on model levels, state variables and diagnostics on pressure levels, near-surface and surface diagnostics, accumulated surface fluxes, and vertically-integrated quantities.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

Zenodo open repository

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Has an open access content policy
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Follows metadata standards
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Enviro-HIRLAM output

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Open, although embargo period will be applied

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

During the project duration, the embargo period for the data will be two years. However, access to the data during the embargo period will be available for the project partners. After the embargo period, the data will be open and accessible.

After the data become publicly available, it will not be possible to identify who access the data.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

According Zenodo rules

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

The embargo period is two years.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Input data provenance will be linked in the metadata

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Use of tools for automatic checks

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Mykhailo Savenets (orcid:0000-0001-9429-6209)

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

WRF output

Modeling for studying aerosol-cloud interactions and cloud microphysics during extreme weather events

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

A set of simulated meteorological variables, microphysics parameters of clouds and precipitation

1.1.5 What is its format?

NetCDF

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1 250 000 000 000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information

- To share information
- To combine with other data

Data will be used to study cloud microphysics, its spatio-temporal variability, and dependence on parametrization.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Weather Research & Forecasting Model (WRF)

<https://www.mmm.ucar.edu/models/wrf>

https://www2.mmm.ucar.edu/wrf/users/physics/mp28_updated.html

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education

Project partners, scientific community in Atmospheric Sciences, national meteorological services, for students, who study atmospheric modeling, as educational data.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

Description Metadata of the WRF output with the data of meteorological variables on model levels.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

Zenodo open repository

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Has an open access content policy
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)

- Assigns PIDs
- Follows metadata standards
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

WRF output

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Open, although embargo period will be applied

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

During the project duration, the embargo period for the data will be two years. However, access to the data during the embargo period will be available for the project partners. After the embargo period, the data will be open and accessible.

After the data become publicly available, it will not be possible to identify who access the data.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

According Zenodo rules

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

The embargo period is two years.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files

- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Input data provenance will be linked in the metadata

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Use of tools for automatic checks

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Anastasiia Chyhareva (orcid:0000-0003-0195-751X)

5.1 Data Security

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- Data sharing

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

Input for Enviro-HIRLAM model

Input data required to run the Enviro-HIRLAM model, set chemical & meteorological initial and boundary conditions; initialize assimilation procedure.

These data include:

- meteorological fields,
- land use/ land cover parameters,
- atmospheric composition;
- antropogenic and natural emissions.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

The following data are required to initialize, set initial and boundary conditions (IC/BC), and run the Enviro-HIRLAM model:

1) meteorological IC/BC: ERA5 reanalysis data from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) (<https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/dataset/ecmwf-reanalysis-v5>);

2) meteorological data for assimilation: meteorological and sea surface temperature observations in BUFR format from the ECMWF archives;

3) land use/ land cover (LULC) input: a few datasets can be used, including ECOCLIMAP-I,II (https://www.umr-cnrm.fr/gmapdoc/IMG/pdf_ECOCLIMAP-SURFEX.pdf), the Pan-European Land Cover Monitoring project (PELCOM) (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/pelcommmap>), The United States Geological Survey (USGS) (<https://www.usgs.gov/>), etc.;

4) chemical IC/BC: 3d-files of aerosol (dust, black and organic carbon, sulfates) and chemical (O3, SO2, NO2, NO, H2O2, OH, NO3, HO2, DMS) compounds from Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) reanalysis (<https://www.ecmwf.int/en/research/climate-reanalysis/camsreanalysis>);

5) emissions: IS4FIRES (<https://is4fires.fmi.fi>), Evaluating the Climate and Air Quality Impacts of Short-Lived Pollutants (IIASA's ECLIPSE, 5th version).

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

1.1.5 What is its format?

GRIB, NetCDF and BUFR

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

3 000 000 000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To develop a product

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

[https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/dataset/ecmwf-reanalysis-v5;](https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/dataset/ecmwf-reanalysis-v5)

https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/datasets/search?f%5B0%5D=sm_field_dataset_urls_filter%3Afield_dataset_archive_url;

<https://opensource.umr-cnrm.fr/projects/ecoclimap/wiki>

[https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/pelcommap;](https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/pelcommap)

<https://www.usgs.gov/>

[https://www.ecmwf.int/en/research/climate-reanalysis/camsreanalysis;](https://www.ecmwf.int/en/research/climate-reanalysis/camsreanalysis)

[https://is4fires.fmi.fi;](https://is4fires.fmi.fi)

[https://iiasa.ac.at/models-tools-data/global-emission-fields-of-air-pollutants-and-ghgs;](https://iiasa.ac.at/models-tools-data/global-emission-fields-of-air-pollutants-and-ghgs)

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Reference

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Input for WRF model

Input data required to run the Weather Research and Forecast (WRF) model, set atmospheric and surface layer conditions.

These data include:

- Meteorological fields,
- Land use/ land cover parameters,
- Surface layer fields,
- Topographic data.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

The following data are required to initialize, set initial and boundary conditions (IC/BC), and run the WRF model:

1) Meteorological fields data, land use/ land cover parameters, surface layer fields on single layers from ERA5 hourly data on single levels database. (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview>) from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) (<https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/dataset/ecmwf-reanalysis-v5>):

- Surface pressure

- Mean sea-level pressure

- Skin temperature/SST

- 2 meter temperature

- 2 meter relative humidity

- 10 meter U and V components of wind

- Soil temperature

- Soil moisture

- Soil height (or terrain height)

2) Meteorological data on pressure layers from ERA5 hourly data on pressure levels database <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis->

era5-pressure-levels?tab=overview from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF)
(<https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/dataset/ecmwf-reanalysis-v5>):

- Temperature
- U and V components of wind
- Geopotential height
- Relative humidity (or specific humidity)

3) Geodata from the ASTER Global Digital Elevation Map Announcement
<https://asterweb.jpl.nasa.gov/gdem.asp>

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

1.1.5 What is its format?

NetCDF and specific WRF input geodata format

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

3 000 000 000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To develop a product

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

[https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/dataset/ecmwf-reanalysis-v5;](https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/dataset/ecmwf-reanalysis-v5)

<https://asterweb.jpl.nasa.gov/gdem.asp>

<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview>

<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-pressure-levels?tab=overview>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

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DataCite Metadata Schema

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Reference

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository
- Linked Open Data

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Powered by

